

LeapFROG: Fixed & Removable Occlusal Guidance

CLINICAL IMAGES

FROG II APPLIANCE

Frog appliance is an intraoral orthodontic appliance for molar distalization introduced by **Walde** in 2006

INDICATIONS

Bilateral molar distalization & Class 2 malocclusion cases

MECHANISM

Each turn of the screw counterclockwise delivers 0.4 mm of distalization. Bodily molar movement after just 4 months

PHYSIOLOGY

Hard tissue changes are seen where the force is applied at the centre of resistance to carry out bodily tooth movement.

ADVANTAGES

Easy assembling & activation, Esthetic, Offers 3-D molar control, Reduced chair time

Before Treatment

After Treatment

Overcorrection

FROGGY APPLIANCE

Froggy appliance is a myofunctional appliance having multiple indications introduced by **Patric Fellus** in 2016

INDICATIONS

Atypical swallowing, Open Bite, Transversal contraction, Crossbite, Increased overjet, Deep bite, Mandibular Protrusion, Bruxism, Posture Alteration, Mouth Breathing, Adenoid disorders, Snoring, Drooling

PHYSIOLOGY

New information is acquired and stored promptly as long term memory forming neuronal circuit as the memory cerebral systems are easily modifiable.

CLINICAL IMAGES

BEFORE

AFTER

MECHANISM

15 minutes every day always during a playful activity. The protocol requires to maintain a correct head position parallel to the floor.

ADVANTAGES

Non-invasive treatment, Comfortable to wear, Cost effective, Improved Speech

REFERENCES

Case of altered tongue position, crossbite, atypical swallowing before and after 6 months of froggy's appliance

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